

The Afghan Resilient Insurgents: Understanding Asymmetric Insurgency in Afghanistan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 01, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 04, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Insurgents, Resilience, Geographic Factors, Military Tactics, Warlords</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5548506</p>	<p><i>The ongoing insurgency for decades in Afghanistan has been resilient and prolonged and even can be termed as chronic. The resilience of the forces which active against foreign empires, powers, and great players since Alexander the Great, to Czarist and British imperial powers and the two hegemony during the Cold War, Afghan insurgent groups is neither defeated nor will be in the future. This paper is aimed at understanding the dynamics, resilience, and nature of the Afghan guerrilla groups that are active against the US and coalition forces. War in Afghanistan cannot be won without handling and defeating the insurgents. For insurgent groups, the favourable terrain, geographic locations, harsh climate, sky Peak Mountains, warlords, and the poor administrative and security reach and control of the Afghan government leads to one of the successful and undefeated guerrilla's insurgents in modern military history.</i></p>

Introduction

The state of Afghanistan was subject to great power interventions, expeditions, and even in the modern time to the mercy of the most advanced hegemon of the time. It is in the nature of the Afghans to fight against the foreign invaders, and they have been successful in this case so far. From the land of bone to the modern military technologies and advancements, the resilient guerrilla groups of Afghanistan can and will never be defeated. The core argument is that the physical terrain, manpower, weak control of governance, physiological dimension, fractious society, and security reach of the government and the insurgent's links and supplies with neighbouring states make them one of the most successful insurgents in the ancient and modern military history and insurgency. Therefore, the below discussion is part of the continuation of efforts to understand the nature and resilience of the Afghan insurgent groups.

Penguin dictionary of international relations defined insurgency as an armed rebellion aimed to overthrow the existing government through violent means (Evans and Newnham, 1998: 22). It should be noted that if the existing government or state responds to the challenge posed by insurgents lead to a civil war or more protracted internal war. Insurgents have two main goals as mentioned by Ewans and Newnham (1998: 22) i.e. Centripetal and Centrifugal. Conventionally, centripetal insurgencies aim to replace and install the regime or government which is more to the interests and preferences of the rebellion. This type of insurgency is started against the colonial rules and for independence at large. For centripetal insurgents, the colonial system was based on forceful means and methods to control their territories and guide their social order without their established norms. The colonial regimes and states perceived small and low levels of insurgency as a threat to their rule and control and often chose a violent means to suppress the resistance groups. Furthermore, within state and authoritarian regimes centripetal insurgency is also evident in many states against the authoritarian rulers of the time.

The other type of insurgency is centrifugal meaning that their basic aim is to establish a new state against the established one. This sort of insurgency is always based on ethnic nationalism. The current examples of this type of insurgency are the insurgency in South Sudan, Indian insurgents in Mizoram and Nagaland. Even the Afghan insurgency against the Soviet Union or against the US can be termed as insurgency based on ethnic lines. Because the majority of the anti-Soviet and anti-US insurgents were recruited through ethnic lines including the Mujahedeen which were mainly Pashtuns dominant or the Northern Alliance which was represented by Tajik and Uzbek nexus. Currently, the Taliban maintained support from Pashtun in the majority. The insurgent's movements use two basic approaches for recruiting the manpower i.e. the sense of ethnic identity and their political obligation or adherence (Evans and Newnham, 1998: 22). Warlords, political figures, and different groups that are in compositions of insurgency recruit manpower from rural areas. The same is true in the context of the Afghan guerrillas as the majority of their manpower belongs to rural areas of Afghanistan.

Just like the Soviet troops heavily bombed the villages and towns in Afghanistan with the aim to drive the population towards cities that can be easily monitored and controlled (McCauley, 2002: 18).

Insurgencies use unconventional means and methods of warfare to achieve their objectives. It will be correct to state that insurgencies follow the Clausewitzian principle that war is the continuation of politics by other means. The logic is to achieve their political objectives against the “incumbent” or oppressor. McCormick defined insurgency as internal conflict and continued power struggle against the established government.

Afghan Taliban, Prelude and World View

At the start of the Taliban movement in Afghanistan, they proclaim that their goal is to restore peace and Afghanistan and has no ambitions for political power and role. The reason behind this approach was that to win the support of the various sections of the Afghan society at large. Later on, when the Taliban consolidated powers, they imposed Islamic Shari laws in Afghanistan. (Najomi, 2008: 134). Rashid (2005: 15) noted that for the Taliban the ideological motives were the powerful driver and bases that pursued their struggle for the restoration of Islamic Laws and revolution. In short for the Taliban the restoration of Islamic Laws and expelling infidel invaders become their primary interests. The Taliban used religion as promises to restore the “God Rule” and also mixed nationalist feelings for greater support (Annee, 1986: 57). Thus, it can be said that the Taliban insurgency in Afghanistan is ideological, restorational in its nature.

The Taliban insurgency in Afghanistan fits in O Neill (1983: 3) categorization as reactionary, conservative, reformist, and restorational. Meaning that the Taliban gain support and mobilize their manpower due to the US invasion and they are also against the currently existing political system and demanding conservative rule and practice. By reformation, the Taliban consider the Afghan constitution as null and void and wants to reform with the Sharia laws. Furthermore, the Taliban also wants to restore the Islamic Emirate of Afghanistan. All the mentioned criteria of insurgencies are portrayed from the Taliban insurgency in Afghanistan.

Factors that Influences Insurgents Campaign

There are various variables and dynamics which influence and impact insurgents’ capability of achieving their goals. These variables, dynamics, or factors include the physical environment, mass support, affective organizational structure and cohesion, and external links for the support of any insurgency. The above-mentioned variables are considered as most important in any insurgent movement and are the key determiner of the success and failure of any insurgency. These variables have put the side with the insurgency in Afghanistan led by the Taliban and these variables are carefully studied. Therefore, I will use these variables in the context of the Taliban insurgency in Afghanistan and the variables subjected to the success of the insurgency.

Environment

While studying any insurgency, the first and foremost variable is to study the physical environment in any chosen insurgency. These include the physical and human dimensions. The physical environment includes terrain, strategically important transportation routes, and infrastructure. The second aspect i.e., humans mainly focus on the demographic, social, economic, and system of the states. Therefore, these are subjected to inquiry below.

Physical Terrain

The geographical terrain is the most important factor in determining the strategy of the insurgents. It is evident from the major historical insurgencies that guerrilla warfare and tactics were waged from the mountains and forests. The classic examples include the Vietnam guerrillas and the insurgency and guerrillas’ tactics in India’s southern provinces.

Terrain

One of the key and important aspects of any insurgency is the terrain and geographic conditions in which the insurgent’s forces operate. For insurgents, the favourable terrain provides hideouts for their operational and central commanding circles but is also suitable against the government and military offensive. The insurgents use the terrain for their operation, planning, and training. The harsh terrain also makes ineffective the offensive against the insurgents including the large-scale military operation, firepower, and even aerial bombardment (Tung, 1963: 200). Thus, the strategic command and key planning figures hide and operate from far-flung terrain.

The previously prefer terrain is visible in the Taliban insurgency in Afghanistan. It can be said that the Taliban insurgency in Afghanistan is a perfect example of geographic choosing for their operational and tactical support. Being operated from rough, sky Peak Mountains which serve as key hideouts for the Taliban are the key to their resilience and success against the US military campaigns. The effects of terrain for both local people and those who are foreign invaders can’t be overlooked. For example, the largest imperial powers and their military might have been proven ineffective in the context of Afghanistan (Nabi, 2006: 224). For the Taliban, the US and the occupying forces to a large were unaware of the nature of the terrain in which the Taliban insurgents operated. Thus, for the Afghan Taliban, the terrain serves as a military advantage.

Speaking from the military and tactical perspectives, the terrain in which large-scale military hardware and personnel deployment become too difficult (Ewans, 2003: 1). This is true for the US giant military power and hardware in Afghanistan against the Taliban.

Geographic contiguity and awareness from the physical terrain are essential for effective, planning, command, and control, both offensive and defensive campaigns, and the continuity of logistical support in any insurgency or military campaign. As compare to mountainous area's insurgency. The urban areas can easily be controlled. Both insurgents and government forces face tactical losses in the urbanized insurgency because for the government the urban areas can easily be monitored (Gurr, 1974: 266).

Logistics, Communications, and role of Infrastructures in Insurgency

The control of strategic routes is essential for the insurgency to be continued. The same is true and significant for the anti-insurgents campaign and military operations. The well-developed infrastructure, roads, and channels of communications are detrimental in government counter-insurgency campaigns or for the insurgents equally. If the infrastructure routes are well-developed across the region or state, the government can easily deploy its troops and military might against the insurgents. However, poor infrastructure, remote terrain, and mountainous regions favour the insurgents. The same fits in one of the classic explanations of the guerrilla's and insurgent's warfare expert Gurr:

“Guerrilla war is common in underdeveloped countries because of poor transportation and communication networks and the isolation of rural areas, which facilitate guerrilla incursions. Free access to rural people enables guerrillas to propagandize, control, and secure support from them ... Given the technological capabilities of the best-equipped modern military forces, the terrain that offers the most effective physical protection for the guerrillas must be mountainous, without roads or tracks, and almost continuously cloud-covered”(Gurr, 1974: p. 264).

If explain the Afghan Taliban insurgency from the above points it becomes evident that Afghanistan lacks a developed system of transport and communication and remote and far-flung rural areas which favour insurgents to operate freely without any counter-offensive fears. On the same note, the insurgents use propaganda to exploit the sentiments of the rural population and gain support. The same is true in the strategies of the Taliban in the rural areas of Afghanistan. Similarly, despite the US and the coalition forces' military superiority and best and modern technologies, they didn't subdue the Afghan Taliban who simply relies on the AK 47 and old Soviet equipment's. The Afghan terrain offers physical protections for the insurgents, and it became too difficult for the anti-insurgent forces to mobilize, launch and deploy troops in the mountainous areas.

The Taliban in Afghanistan controlled the key strategic and communication routes to fuel and continue their insurgency across the country. The Taliban insurgency continued and channelled through three main strategic routes in Afghanistan.

Taliban logistical roads

Map, 1(Dorsorno, 2009: 24)

There are three major strategically important routes along Pakistan and Afghanistan border which is extended and essential for the control over the whole heartland (Central and Southern Afghanistan). These are the same routes which contested and controlled by the anti-Soviet Mujahedeen in the early eighties. These include:

- The first routes start from Parachinar in Pakistan to the south of the Kabul and beyond. The Taliban has always considers to influence and control in the Logar Province. The Azrah district of Logar Province is strategically serve as a gate way to the southern Kabul and beyond. According to the report and local populations of the Jaji tribes in the Khost Province, the Taliban constantly argued unconditional surrender with aim to control over the route for fuelling and channel their insurgency. This main route goes around Kandahar, Hazarajat Province, upwards to Aimaq. This route is important to reach out to the Farah Province and to the southern Maymana and Mazar-i-Sharif.
- The second most important route span over Zabul Province and extended towards the South, West and Northern Part of Afghanistan. From strategic and logistical point of view, this route and road is important tube which enabled the Taliban insurgents to further extend their presence and operation to the Northern part including Ghanzi, Wardak and Logar. Helmand, Herat, Badghris are strategically speaking on the “stone throw distance” and the Taliban have total control and influence there.
- The third strategically pivotal route is on the Kunar Province starting from the Kunar and extending to north of the Kabul and Jalalabad. One of the basic reason and importance of the Kunar province is that it remains strong hold of the Hezb-i-Islami of Afghanistan, the provident group of the Taliban. The

previously mentioned group maintained huge presence and influence in the Kunar Province (Dorsoorno, 2009: 23).

Speaking from the Taliban strategy and logistical point of view, it becomes clear that the Taliban control major and minor strategic routes of the Afghanistan with the immense influence and capability to attack mobilize and retreat. It would not be wrong to conclude the inference that the Taliban control the main heart and channel routes of Afghanistan and it is too difficult for both the US and the Afghan governments and forces to undo the Taliban influences.

The Human Environment

Demography and Human/Population Distribution

In any insurgency and movement, demographic factor play a key role in their movement. For example if the population is concentrated in the urban areas, cities and major towns, it become easy for the government to control and cut links of the insurgents with the population. Thus, for the government and anti-insurgent forces it becomes easy to identify, isolate and counter the insurgents in urbanized areas and cities. It becomes too difficult for the insurgents to maintain their influences, bases and support in the urbanized areas.

The same is to in the context of the Taliban insurgency in Afghanistan where they have nominal control and influence over urban areas and including major cities. It is important to mention that nearly eighty percent population in Afghanistan dwell in the rural areas and some twenty percent in the urban areas and towns (Najomi, 2002: 1-2). The rural areas and population serve as a major protective grounds where insurgents operate and culminate and executive their plan and propaganda (Johnson and Mason, 2007: 73).

For the US and the Afghan forces it was too difficult to initiate counter insurgency campaign in nearly eighty percent population and far flung urban areas. For them, the first step was to secure and pull back the Taliban fighters control and hold the control and becomes too difficult to deny the fall-back into the Taliban insurgent's control. Thus, it shows that one of the major reasons for the failure of anti-insurgents campaign in Afghanistan is due to diverse and rural roots of the insurgents across the population and state (Johnson and Mason, 2007: 73). For the insurgents the rural and mountainous terrain is conducive for their activities as compared to the urban areas.

Social Structure and Support for the Taliban Insurgency

For insurgency social division in any society, class structure, ethnic division, religious factors, etc. are the key variables in the development of insurgency. If a majority of the ethnic group is deprived as, compare to other ethnics groups it becomes easy to mobilize them for insurgency (O'Neill, 2005: 61). When the ethnic pattern is diverse and based on different groups and localities, the insurgent movement can't be solidified (Crews and Tarzi, 2008: 11). The internal frictions in the insurgent movements become evident and affect their cohesion and insurgency at large. The anti-insurgents forces or states can use ethnic card to diversify and minimize the insurgent organization and cohesiveness.

The social structure and ethnic composition of Afghanistan have favoured the insurgent movement that might be the Mujahedeen struggle against the Soviet Union or the Taliban resistance against the US and coalition forces. Many of the dynamics is shared by the Afghan state and society which experts on the insurgency believe can contribute in this context. This includes mountainous terrain, larger section of the society below the poverty level, traditional families with large population, cross border support, safe havens, illicit drug trafficking and their finance (Fearon and Laitin, 2003: 78-80). The state and society of Afghanistan represent all the above mention dynamics. All these variables and dynamics make the Afghan Taliban undefeatable and emerged as one the resilience insurgency as compare to the modern and superior military power of the time.

Insurgency and Popular Support

Public and popular support of the major section of the society or state is necessary for insurgency. From strategic point of view, public support and backing is necessary for insurgency and their success of failure. This will enable the insurgent against the government or opposing forces to contain the insurgent propaganda and their movement.

Insurgents take popular support in two forms in any society or state. The first form of support is provided by individual who support and sympathy with the insurgent's movement and the second is those who become part of the movement and devoted themselves (O'Neill, 2005: 61). Thus, they provide intelligence sharing and information, sanctuaries, manpower, moral and financial support (Trinquier, 1964: 17). Both form of support for the insurgency is important and cannot be ignored from their perspective (Cozier, 1970: 16). In case of Afghanistan, both religious and ethnic appeals serve as a binding and recruiting ground for the Taliban insurgent. On many occasions, the Taliban exploit the social, economic and political weakness of the Afghan states in order to legitimize and gain support from the masses.

The Taliban propaganda and tools for popular support among masses is effective and based on their strategy for wining hearts and minds. The Taliban affectively used the occupation of foreign forces as threat to common Afghan's culture, tradition and Islamic way of life with aim to win the support. Similarly, they also portray to the people the inefficiency of the local and central government in solving the miseries of the common peoples. The Taliban strategy for gaining public support and sentiments seems successful across the country. These

isolate and marginalize the US and the Afghan government counter-insurgency measure and political and administrative reach and control. The Taliban insurgents also established their parallel administrative setups in majority districts of the Afghanistan. In doing so, the Taliban successfully recruited other ethnic and non-Pashtun elements in their circles (Dorrnsoro, 2009: 7).

It is to mention that majority of the Pashtuns considered the US presence as illegitimate along with the religious sentiments as infidel and outsider power who must be expelled from their homeland. The common Pashtuns culture and traditions do not support the occupying force and power and consider them as a *Dushman* (enemy). Moreover, the US military operation antagonized the common masses due to civilian and innocent killing in the villages. In the continuing violence and target of the innocent civilian, for example in the Balkh Province during 2008 and onward, the US Special Forces conducted military and search operations by targeting the suspected elements of the Taliban. However, the perception in the local people is that the US raped and dishonours the women and girls (Dorrnsoro, 2009: 7). This resulted in the greater antagonization among the local population. Thus, the US and the Afghan security forces desperately failed to build their soft image in the strong hold of the Taliban.

Furthermore, the civilian targeting by the US security forces has political repercussion and backlashes for the Afghan state. Through Afghanistan media channel the picture and graphic videos are shown which anger the local population who often connects these actions as committed by the Soviet Union. Thus, the popular perception in many part of Afghanistan about the US is the enemy of them (Dorrnsoro, 2009: 7).

In any offensive insurgency or counterinsurgency, organization plays a key role from both materials, operational, tactical and planning levels. Gurr (1974: 274) studied any insurgent group from organizational level which include scope of the organization, complexity, cohesion in organization and the major functions. Insurgents always try to increase their memberships in villages and major cities and towns. The same is true in the context of Afghanistan which the former intelligence director Saleh describes in his report as:

“The Taliban’s use of recruitment techniques in the ongoing stage is becoming sophisticated. They approach tribes, sub-tribes and communities in the villages. They want them to sever their relationship with the government and also preach to the population to support the jihad against the Americans and the government which they consider the infidel” (Saleh, 2006; p.3).

Similarly, the insurgents establish the computable government structure at local and regional levels. This was evident from the Taliban strategy from establishing various local and administrative structures parallel with the central Afghan government (Dorrnsoro, 2009: 8).

Furthermore, the reason behind overall strategy of the Taliban in Afghanistan is to broaden its support, recruit, and marginalize the central Afghan government which they consider as illegitimate and puppet of the US. In various provinces of Afghanistan the Taliban established their parallel administration and shadow governments. Accordingly, in more than 30 provinces, the Taliban has influence and control with their pro-governors and administration (Cordesman, 2010: 3).

As Hyde (1968: 33-34) noted that insurgents form alliance for tactical purpose with the various groups which oppose the central government if apply on the Taliban strategy in Afghanistan is valid and evident from the Taliban and Al-Qaida nexus, non-state actors and criminals. Moreover, there are regular and part time fighters fighting on the behalf of the Taliban and work as a major man power. The Taliban efficiency and well managed structure attract its followers including the material benefits and psychological satisfactions. It means that those who are engage against the Afghan government and US forces has broadly two objectives for their participation which include material and political benefits and a religious and psychological which Taliban called the holy war or dying in the path of Allah (Dorrnsoro, 2009: 28).

Furthermore, for the insurgents groups, cohesion is the key variable which determines their ability and resilience. Meanings that, if there is unity in the insurgent ranks they can effectively formulate plans and execute and implement their agendas. Insurgents delegate authority to local commanders with central planning and strategic command. In the classic insurgency campaign as pointed by Mao that if there is centralized command, there would be little chances of the partisan against their adversaries. For them, they should decentralize their command into local commanders, arms groups and should attain maximum public support (O’Neill, 2005: 25). The same strategy was used by the Afghan Taliban against the US and the Afghan security forces.

It is important question to answer that how the Taliban commander exercises control over rest of commanders at local levels. In this context, the geographic contiguity of Afghanistan makes difficult for the central command of the Taliban to monitor and exercise its control over the commanders in charge various areas and fronts. For the local commands, they central leaderships issue *layeha amal* (Code of Conduct) which challenged and provided to various local commanders. Spiegel (2006) noted that the Taliban issue a booklet known as their code of conduct and distributed to various commanders. This portray that the Taliban has the ability to coordinate and control all restive commander through proper channel of communication and guidelines. However, McKiernan a former NATO commander in Afghanistan noted that the Taliban insurgency remains poorly coordinated at both operational and strategic levels.

It becomes evident that the Taliban is den-centralized command and control system under which the regional commanders act upon the guidelines issue by the central authority. This also shows that the Taliban insurgency in Afghanistan has coherence in their struggle and is loyal to their supreme commander (Gall, 2008).

According to an interview of Mansur Dadullah with Aljazeera in 2006, he stated that the Afghan Taliban and Al-Qaida were in nexus and agreed on sharing information and cooperating of strategic and tactical levels with each other's. He further added that the coordination between Al-Qaida and Taliban are strong, and we will further endorse it (Al-Sahab, 2007). This shows what Mao pointed for successes of any insurgent movement the Afghan Taliban followed the same path and print.

Similarly, to maintain order and unity in their ranks, the insurgent's movements formulate and stress on common attitude, code of conduct and organizational restriction. In this context, among the insurgent group and its members, ideology work as a binding force and key of cohesion (Livingstone, 1968: 4). By following the ideology, the insurgents formulate their collective worldview, direction, goals and political and social posture and practice. It is necessary that all the insurgent groups has the same and unifying ideology, however, if the difference on ideological matter occur then it will lead to splitting in different groups and organization.

The Taliban insurgent's ideology is subject to major inquiries and debate from various experts. Among them Rashid (2000: 4) pointed that the Taliban ideology is based on the conservative interpretation of Sharia Laws and extreme form and following of Deobandi school of thought and mix of Pashtunwali code of conduct across the state of Afghanistan. Giustozzi (2008: 12) argue that the Taliban ideology was mixture of Islamic teachings practiced in rural areas with the following of Deobandi School of thoughts and lay emphasis of the orthodox and fundamental interpretation of Sharia laws and implementation.

On the Taliban insurgents ideology, Sullivan (2007: 100-101) mentioned that Taliban ideology is based on the traditional beliefs mix with Pashtuns traditions and culture who are in constant struggle to restore the old Islamic societal ideals. However, after the 2001, the ideology of the Taliban also called new-Taliban with their old ideology but modified with the number of global jihadi groups such as Al-Qaida which promote global rhetoric of their ideology. Furthermore, the neo-Taliban to large extent is more flexible from the old Taliban in their interpretation of the classic Sharia Laws (Giustozzi, 2008:12).

From the above one can draw inference that ideology is the common bounds which skewed various insurgents groups in Afghanistan altogether. Ideology provides moral, ethical and palling code of conduct for the Taliban and various insurgents in Afghanistan. The Taliban ideology can be termed as based on religious inspiration and mix up with Pashtuns code of conduct called Pashtunwali.

External Support

External support is the key and important variable which insurgents seek from states or other groups. This external support includes and might be moral, political, material, financial, and sanctuaries (O'Neill, 2005: 13).

By moral support it mean that a third state acknowledge and recognize the insurgents movement and their struggle for just cause. Pro-insurgent states provide political support due to shared strategic objectives and interests to the insurgent groups. Moreover, the insurgents also got material support including arms, finance, manpower, technical assistance, logistics, and sanctuaries from the supporting states. Hence material support is necessary for the continuation of insurgent moments in the long term.

Broadly, the insurgent's external support can be categorized into two forms. In first form and case, the foreign states, the international diasporas, and their likeminded groups provide directs assistance in shape of money, training and logistics, political support and through diplomacy (Byman, 2005: 53). In case of external support, the insurgents receive notable leadership and foreign fighters also which made their movement global famous. Through external support insurgents needs basics necessities to sustain their movement by assuring flow of material goods, money and arms. They also need uninterrupted supply and information to continue their insurgency (Jones, 2008: 42).

The second form of support usually includes the availability of cross border sanctuaries for the insurgents. The insurgents use foreign territory as a safe haven for planning and operating their insurgency. The safe heavens if accessible to the insurgents, then there is little chances for the successes of the counter-insurgency strategy (Byman, 2005: 78).

In case of the Afghan Taliban, they have cross-border sanctuaries in their neighbour's states including Pakistan. The US and the Afghan governments constantly putted pressure on Pakistan to eliminate the insurgent bases and safe havens on their territory. The US also believes that the Taliban have received major supplies, material and technical support from Pakistan and their intelligence agencies. The Haqqani Network and Quetta Shura were the main source of concerns for US in the counter-insurgency strategy in Afghanistan (McChrystal, 2005). The former Federally Administered Areas (FATA) serves as major sanctuaries of the Taliban insurgents including the border areas of Pakistan (Giustiozzi, 83).

It is important to note that the Taliban freely operated from the Pakistani territory in the past and since 2001. However, due to Pakistan national security problems and backlashes of the providing sanctuaries on their territory result in wide and open debate in Pakistan's foreign and security circles by using its territory against Afghanistan. In this direction, Pakistan initiated fencing the puros border with Afghanistan which will be fully

sealed and it will be difficult for the insurgents to freely operate across the border as they were in the past. It seems logical from Pakistan's side that they can't fully control the porous and open border with approximately more than one million people daily cross the border. Hence, the fencing of the border with Afghanistan can improve the stopping of the cross border infiltration across the border.

It becomes clear that for the success of insurgent's movement, the safe heavens across the border is necessary for their operational and strategic aspects without which they can't operationalized and implement their plans. As far as the Taliban insurgency in Afghanistan is concerned, they used Pakistan's border areas as ground for planning and sanctuaries in against the US and the Afghan forces. However, with the emergence of the neo-Taliban in Afghanistan questioned Pakistan's use of territory and bases. The neo-Taliban has although nexus with the religious organizations in Pakistan but at larger context, their struggle is indigenous in nature in Afghanistan.

Conclusion

It is to be inferred after analysis of various factors in Afghanistan and the variables which make the Taliban insurgent's one of the resilient and undefeated. From both tactical and operational perspectives, the US badly failed to neutralize the Taliban insurgency in Afghanistan along with the Afghan security forces. There are various dynamics that make the Afghan Taliban undefeatable by the major military power of the time i.e. US along with NATO. In this context, the first variable is the geographic terrain and locations of Afghanistan and the insurgent's tactical and guerrilla warfare strategies. Winning both on the battlefield and people's hearts and minds considers significant for both resisting and offensive forces. It seems from the Taliban strategy of galvanized war for religious cause and duty along with the presence of strong cultural sentiments. The US on its part failed to the hearts and minds of the common Afghans and its efforts eroded by various variables.

After much of its efforts, the US and the Afghan forces failed to castrate cross-border links and support to the Afghan Taliban. It is important to resist the superpower and fight for "just war" or "just case" using and glorifying religious sentiments and moral dimensions. Winning both on the battlefield and people's hearts and minds is considering significant for both resisting and offensive forces. It seems from the Taliban strategy of galvanized war for religious cause and duty along with the presence of strong cultural sentiments. The US on its part failed to win the hearts and minds of the common Afghans and its efforts eroded by various variables.

The Taliban's world view and propaganda is appealing to the common masses along with glorifying their religious belief and the protection of uncontrolled state by many empires. Taliban use religion along with political fault lines for their popular support against the foreign troops. Hence, it is true that tribalism, honour, martyrdom, and resilience to foreign occupation are the key factors that contributed to the Taliban prolong and successful insurgency against the US.

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